

Trophic interactions and land use impacts in fish communities in headwater tropical streams

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Introduction

Tropical streams have been impacted by riparian deforestation, which causes habitat loss, decrease in the input of allochthonous resources and increase of light incidence. Associated with nutrient input it is expected to cause an increase of autochthonous production (periphytic algae). Thus the aquatic biota should respond to these anthropic impacts through their trophic interactions.

Objectives & Methods

To determine these responses we analyzed the trophic ecology of fish and food web structure in 20 streams (3rd order) of four watersheds in the Atlantic Forest in Southeastern Brazil. The streams are arranged in a gradient of impacts related to the watershed land use and the local structural and limnological features. We analyzed fish stomach contents and stable isotopes of carbon in fish muscle and their resources.

Results

The abundance of insectivorous and omnivorous fish increased as the percentage of canopy cover decreased (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Relationships between canopy cover (%) and abundance of insectivorous and omnivorous fish in 20 Atlantic Forest streams, Southeastern Brazil. * $p < 0.1$

High food web specialization (H2 metric) was related to streams with higher canopy cover, indicating higher resource partitioning among fish species (a, Figure 2).

Decreasing canopy cover led to a less number of links per specimen within the Algivorous-insectivorous guild (b, Figure 2).

Figure 2: Relationships between canopy cover (%) and (a) food web specialization, and (b) link per specimen within Algivorous-insectivorous guild in 20 Atlantic Forest streams, Southeastern Brazil. * $p < 0.01$

The local land use impact (% of canopy cover) determined the most variation of periphytic algae carbon values in the studied streams (a, Figure). Carbon variations in the fish guilds were in part a reflection of the periphytic algae variations, which was shown to be the main source of basal carbon for fish communities (b, Figure 3).

Figure 3: Relationship between (a) canopy cover (%) and periphytic algae, and between (b) periphytic algae and four trophic guilds of fish in 20 Atlantic Forest streams, Southeastern Brazil. * $p < 0.001$

Discussion & Conclusion

Local impact gradients (canopy cover) determined the structure and the trophic interactions in the fish communities and within some of the trophic guilds. Responses were similar for the community level as compared to within-guild responses. Species were less specialized in the community level whereas the individuals within the insectivorous guild had less links with their resources in streams impacted by riparian deforestation.